

Early Flood Detection System

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Abstract - Flooding is one of the most common natural disasters that causes significant damage to infrastructure, agriculture, and human life. The impact often becomes severe due to the absence of early warning systems, especially in smaller regions where advanced monitoring solutions are not available. In this project, I designed and developed an early flood detection system that continuously monitors water levels and alerts users when the water rises beyond predefined thresholds. An ultrasonic sensor is used to measure the distance between the sensor and water surface, enabling accurate detection of rising water levels. Based on these measurements, different warning stages are indicated using light emitting diodes and a buzzer. The system also sends real time notifications through a mobile application, allowing remote monitoring and quicker response. The system is built using a microcontroller that processes sensor data and controls alert mechanisms. The design focuses on simplicity, low cost, and reliability, making it suitable for deployment in flood prone areas. Testing showed consistent performance and timely alerts, demonstrating the system's effectiveness in providing early flood warnings.

Index Terms - Early Warning system, flood detection, internet of things, real-time monitoring

I. Introduction

Floods are among the most destructive natural disasters and can occur due to heavy rainfall, dam overflow, poor drainage systems, or sudden accumulation of water. In many cases, people become aware of flooding only when the situation becomes dangerous. This delay increases the

risk to life and property. Traditional flood monitoring systems are often expensive and require continuous manual monitoring. These systems are not suitable for small-scale deployment or remote locations. With the advancement in IoT and embedded systems, it has become possible to design low-cost and efficient monitoring solutions. In this project, I designed an Early Flood Detection System using ESP32 and ultrasonic sensor technology. The system continuously measures water level and categorizes it into safe, warning, and danger levels. Based on the detected level, LEDs change color and a buzzer activates to alert nearby individuals. Additionally, notifications are sent using Blynk for remote monitoring. The aim of this project is to create a simple, reliable, and low-cost flood detection system that can be easily deployed and maintained.

II. Problem Statement

Floods often occur without early warning, especially in areas with poor drainage systems or sudden heavy rainfall. Existing flood monitoring systems are expensive, complex, or require manual observation. Therefore, there is a need for an affordable, automated, and reliable early flood detection system that continuously monitors water level and alerts users before conditions become dangerous.

III. Objectives

The main objectives of this projects are:

- To design a low-cost early flood detection system
- To monitor water level continuously

- To provide visual alerts using LEDs
- To send real-time notifications using IoT
- To design a compact and easy-to-deploy system

IV. Components Used

- A. ESP32 Microcontroller:
ESP32 acts as the main controller of this system. It handles the sensor data and controls LEDs, buzzer and IoT communication. ESP32 was selected for its built-in Wifi, number of general purpose pins, low power consumption and memory.
- B. HC-SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor:
The HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensor is used to measure water level. It works by sending ultrasonic waves and calculating distance on the received echo.
- C. LED indicators:
Three LEDs are used to indicate different flood alerts:
Green LED is used for safe level
Orange LED is used for warning level
Red LED is used for danger level.
- D. Active Buzzer:
The active buzzer provides audible alerts when water level reaches warning or danger levels.
- E. Breadboard and Jumper Wires:
These two are used for circuit connections and building the prototype.
- F. Power Supply:
2 3.7v lithium ion batteries are used to power the system.
- G. Blynk IoT Platform:
Blynk is used for real-time cloud based notification and monitoring.
- H. Resistor:
Resistors are used across the system to prevent any voltage differences and shorting of the circuits.

V. Methodology

This system continuously measures the distance between the ultrasonic sensor and the water surface. When water level increases, the measured distance decreases. The ESP32 processes this data and compares it with predefined threshold values.

If the water level is below the safe threshold, the green LED remains ON. When water rises above the warning threshold, the orange LED turns ON and the buzzer activates intermittently. When water reaches danger level, the red LED turns ON and the buzzer activates continuously.

Simultaneously, notifications are sent through Blynk, allowing users to monitor the system remotely.

Figure 1. General Block Diagram

VI. Working Principle

The ultrasonic sensor sends wave signals toward the water surface and gets reflected back. These reflected pulses are received by the sensor. ESP32 calculates the distance using the time taken for the signal to return.

$$\text{Distance} = (\text{Time} \times \text{Speed of Sound}) / 2$$

As water rises, the measured distance decreases over time.

The system categorizes the water level into:

- Safe Level
- Warning Level
- Danger Level

Based on these levels, LEDs and buzzers are activated.

VII. Circuit Explanation

The ultrasonic sensor is connected to ESP32 using trigger and echo pins. LEDs are connected to GPIO pins through resistors. The buzzer is connected to another GPIO pin.

Pin Configuration:

Green LED — GPIO 27

Orange LED — GPIO 26

Red LED — GPIO 25

Ultrasonic Trigger — GPIO 14

Ultrasonic Echo — GPIO 12

Buzzer — GPIO 33

ESP32 reads sensor data and controls outputs accordingly.

Figure 2. Hardware Prototype

7. Activate buzzer if required
8. Send notification to Blynk platform
9. Repeat continuously

Figure 3. System Workflow Diagram

VIII. Software Implementation

This system is programmed using Arduino IDE which is a globally available coding interface for ESP32 microcontroller. This code is written in embedded C. The program is structured to continuously read data from the ultrasonic sensor and accordingly updates the output. The built-in WiFi module is also activated for WiFi connection.

Blynk IoT, a popular basic IoT cloud platform is used to display water levels, distance and other data and sends live alerts. Real-time monitoring also occurs in the Blynk platform and the ESP32 sends data to the Blynk cloud using WiFi.

The software consists of:

- Sensor reading logic
- Threshold comparison logic
- LED control logic
- Buzzer control logic
- Flood rate index calculation logic
- Blynk notification logic

IX. System Flow

1. System powers on
2. ESP32 connects to the WiFi
3. Ultrasonic sensor reads distance
4. ESP32 calculates water level
5. Threshold values are compared
6. LEDs are activated based on the water level

X. Results and Testing

The system was tested under different water level conditions. The ultrasonic sensor detected real-time changes in the water level based on which different LEDs and buzzer signals were produced. Real-time data was also sent to the cloud platform.

Blynk notifications were received in real-time. The system responded very quickly and precisely. This testing confirmed that the system is very much reliable for real-word early-flood scenarios.

Figure 4. Arduino Serial Monitor Output

Figure 5. Low Flood Reading in Blynk Platform

Figure 6. High Flood Reading in Blynk Platform

Figure 7. Web Application Alert

XI. Advantages

- The system is inexpensive which helps replacing easy
- Deployment of this system is also very easy
- Real-time data is being monitored through the day and is sent to a cloud based system
- Remote notifications are received in case of early floods.
- Consumes very low power which increases longevity of the system

XII. Limitations

- As the current ultrasonic sensor is not waterproof the sensor maybe affected by heavy rains
- WiFi connectivity is necessary for the system to run efficiently and transfer data to the cloud.
- The sensing range is limited to up-to 400cm.

XIII. Future Scope

This current system is very well optimised but there is clear room for future improvements.

- An GSM module can be added for SMS alerts
- The current battery based power system can be shifted to a solar based system
- Multiple sensor nodes can be used for better calculations
- Cloud data analytics can be improved with improved deep/machine learning algorithms
- An proper mobile application can be built along with the existing web application for ease of use

XIV. Conclusion

The Early Flood Detection System was successfully designed and implemented using ESP32 and ultrasonic sensors. The system effectively monitors water level and provides early alerts using LEDs, buzzer, and IoT notifications. This project demonstrates that a simple and low-cost solution can significantly improve flood preparedness.

The system can be deployed in various flood-prone areas and further enhanced with additional features. The project successfully achieved the objective of developing a reliable early flood detection system.

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